

The Influence of Price, Product Quality and Promotion on Buying Interest in Millennial Garden Ornamental Plants

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Abstract:- The purpose of this research analyzes the effect of price, product quality, and promotion on buying interest in ornamental plants. The data used is sourced from millennial garden consumers who have purchased and potential buyers by using purposive sampling with a total of one hundred in the selection of respondents. Data processing methods using multiple linear regression. The results of this study are partial shows that prices have no significant effect on buying interest, product quality has a significant effect on buying interest, and promotion has a significant effect on buying interest.

Keywords:- Price, Product Quality, Promotion and buying interest.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the outbreak of Covid-19 in Indonesia, all activities of Indonesian society have limitations and rules that must be obeyed. Changes in the work system as one of the government's efforts to prevent the spread of covid-19. Limiting all community activities that can only be done at home, it turns out to be bored so that it is encouraged to look for new activities to fill spare time. One of them that is in great demand is caring for ornamental plants. With the many benefits of ornamental plants, people began to look for, buy and care for ornamental plants, and even cultivate them. Along with the changes in community activities, the sale of ornamental plants is increasing. Since the co-19 pandemic

has had many impacts in various aspects, especially the economic aspect, including the agricultural sector, especially agribusiness actors. With the increase in new interest in the community in ornamental plants, since then the ornamental plant business has become the most rapidly growing business and almost all types of ornamental plants sell well in the market. So that the impact of a good economic increase for agribusiness actors.

Along with the increase in sales of ornamental plants, it also has an impact on the sale of ornamental plants at Millennial Garden. Millennial garden is one of the MSMEs engaged in the ornamental plant business with its sub-business of potted ornamental plants with the type of Anthurium. There are two types of Anthurium known by the public, namely leaf Anthurium and flower Anthurium.

Millennial Garden was founded in January 2019 which is domiciled in Kp Ranji tengah RT 04 RW 09 Kebonpedes Village Kebonpedes District Kebonpedes Sukabumi Regency Postal Code 43194 Jawa Barat Indonesia. Among the products sold are Philodendron Darklord, Janda Bolong, Melano, Difrenbecia, Wave of Love, Sensiviera etc. and only in 2021 added a green house branch in Bandung Ujung Berung.

Millennial garden marketing is done online and offline. Online marketing is done through marketplaces including; Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, Tokopedia.

➤ *Product and Market Place Images*

Fig 1 Product and Market Place Images

Revenue in 2019, 2020 and 2021 during the covid 19 pandemic increased from 20,600,000 (twenty million six hundred thousand rupiah) then to IDR 66,000,000 (sixty-six million rupiah) and IDR 67,200,000 (Sixty-seven million two hundred thousand rupiah). The following graph and table data:

Fig 2 Revenue Graph

Fig 3 Revenue graph

Fig 4.Revenue Graph

Fig 5.Revenue Table

Fig 6.Revenue Target Table

➤ Price Comparison Table with Other Stores

Table 1

Millennial Garden Plant Price List	
Plant Type	Price
Cycads	IDR 35,000
Peperomia Obtusifolia Plain Green	IDR 15,000
Siklok	IDR 35,000
Monstera Deliciosa	IDR 85,000
Aloe Vera	IDR 10,000
Aglonema Moonlight	IDR 1,000,000
Aglonema Khocin	IDR 200,000
Aglonema Flower Seeds 9 Types	IDR 550,000
Aglonema Lotus Seedlings	IDR 1,800,000
Bromelia Neoregelia Purple Brush	IDR 420,000
Monstera Deliciosa Variegata	IDR 4,000,000
Agronema Ayu Green Super	IDR 755,000
Aglonema Red Sumatra	IDR 350,000

Table 2

X Store Ornamental Plant Price List	
Plant Type	Price
Cycads	IDR 30,000
Peperomia Obtusifolia Plain Green	IDR 20,000
Siklok	IDR 40,000
Monstera Deliciosa	IDR 95,000
Aloe Vera	IDR 8,000
Aglonema Moonlight	IDR 870,000
Aglonema Khocin	IDR 195,000
Aglonema Flower Seeds 9 Types	IDR 600,000
Aglonema Lotus Seedlings	IDR 1,750,000
Bromelia Neoregelia Purple Brush	IDR 420,000
Monstera Deliciosa Variegata	IDR 4,200,000
Agronema Ayu Green Super	IDR 745,000
Aglonema Red Sumatra	IDR 360,000

➤ Theoretical Studies

Price is a measure of the value of a product that generates revenue. Prices are very easy to adjust. The covid-19 pandemic is no exception.

Table 3 Price Table

Price	Consumer Price Affordability	1. Able to buy products at the price set by the company
		2. Feeling the price of a product is "cheap"
	Price Match with Product Quality	1. They don't mind paying more for a better quality product.
		2. Feeling that the price of the product is not expensive, because it is balanced with the quality of the product.
	Price Match with Consumer Benefits	1. Deciding to buy a product, because they feel that the product has many benefits.
		2. Willing to pay a high price because the benefits of the product are large/many.
	Price in accordance with ability	1. Consumers consider price, before deciding to buy a product.
		2. Deciding to buy an expensive product, because there is a discount on offer.
		3. Decided to buy a product at a high price, with a periodic payment period (credit)

The quality of a product is a product of value that satisfies the consumer, so it happens how the product has value that can satisfy the consumer physically and psychologically. This indicates that an item or result contains attributes or qualities (Kotler and Armstrong 2015: 224). Factors that affect product quality include product function, product appearance, and product cost.

Table 4 Product Quality Table

Product Quality	Shape	1. The product model looks attractive 2. The texture of the product is attractive and pleasant to the touch
	Performance	1. Products have the best quality assurance 2. Product quality is good, but the price is not expensive
	Conformance to Specifications	1. Products in line with market trends 2. The product matches what the customer wants
	Resilience	1. Product is not damaged even if used everyday 2. Product is not damaged even if placed in stressful situations
	Aesthetics	1. The beauty of the product attracts the eye 2. Aspects and ornaments in the product make consumers feel happy to see it
	Perceived Quality	1. Product quality is in accordance with what consumers imagine 2. The product has advantages, in accordance with what consumers expect

Promotion is an activity carried out to attract customers to buy goods or services. Several factors influence the promotion, namely the funds used for promotion, the nature of the market and the type of product offered.

Table 5 Promotion Table

Promotion	Sales Promotion	1. Providing discounts 2. Providing <i>buy one get one</i> free promo
	Direct Marketing	1. How to communicate in person, telephone quote 2. How to communicate in person, <i>e-mail</i> offers
		3. How to communicate directly, offer through <i>social media</i> accounts
	Personal Selling	1. Consumers feel confident in the quality of a product, for example trusting the quality of products with certain <i>brands</i> 2. Consumers feel confident with the <i>image</i> of a particular <i>brand</i> , so they immediately believe in any product it creates.

Purchase interest is a response to the feeling of liking that arises when consumers see a product but have not yet reached the buying stage. The factors that influence buying interest are psychological, cultural, memory, and personal.

Table 6 Purchase Intention Table

Purchase Intention	Attention	1. Consumers find out more about a product that is considered interesting.
		2. Consumers periodically observe products that are considered attractive (see product reviews on <i>YouTube</i> pages, visit product exhibitions)
	Interest	1. Consumers feel interested in finding out more about a product (e.g. asking those who already own the product, reading articles related to a product).
		2. Consumers approach a product.
	Desire	1. Consumers feel curious about a product.
		2. Feeling like owning a product.

There are several variables that influence buying interest such as: Brand Image, Lifestyle, Price, Product Quality, Promotion, and Aesthetics.

Fig 7. Pre-Survey Table

Table 7 Pre-Survey Questionnaire Results

No.	Statement	Variables	Number of voters
			Description
1	I am interested in buying millennial garden ornamental plants because of the brand image	Brand Image	No one chooses
2	I am interested in buying millennial garden ornamental plants because of the lifestyle	Lifestyle	No one chooses
3	I am interested in buying millennial garden ornamental plants because of the price	Price	3 people
4	I am interested in buying millennial garden ornamental plants because of the product quality	Product Quality	5 people
5	I am interested in buying milenial garden ornamental plants because of promotions	Promotion	2 people
6	I am interested in buying mienia garden ornamental plants because of aesthetics	Aesthetics	No one chooses

Source: Pre-Survey Questionnaire Data Processing Results (2022)

Fig 8. Frame Work Thinking Table

From the results of the problem, the Pre Survey Table and the Framework Thinking, the authors are interested in researching with the title "THE EFFECT OF PRICE, PRODUCT QUALITY, AND PROMOTION ON BUYING INTEREST IN MILENIAL GARDEN PLANTS".

II. METHODS

This study was conducted to determine consumer interest in purchasing ornamental millennial horticultural plants, which is influenced by multiple factors such as price, product quality, and advertising. The variables used in this study are: Price (X1), product quality (X2), promotion (X3), interest in purchase (Y).

The research population is all consumers of Millennial Garden products, totaling 100 people. The sample for this study was 100 people using non-probability sampling and target sampling techniques. Probability sampling is a sampling technique that is carried out when the probability of each member of the population being selected as a sample is unknown. So you can use this method to find your next sample. Consistency with research objectives (Azwar, 2018). Similar to the targeted sampling technique, the determination of the sample is based on certain criteria that must be met by the individuals selected to be sampled (Sugiyono, 2014 in Satria, 2017).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings about the effect of variable X1 or price on the willingness to buy of millennial garden consumers show that there is no effect between X1 (price) and Y (willingness to buy) for millennial garden ornamental consumers . This is related to the regression results obtained, which are $0.710 > 0.05$ and the t count values are $2.374 > t$ table. 1.96. From this we can conclude that H1 was rejected. In other words, X1 (price) has no effect on Y (intention to buy). This finding is also supported by previous findings Guen conducted in her 2018 survey. It is said that price does not influence purchase intention. With reference to the above results, we can conclude that there is no significant effect between X1 (price) and Y (purchase interest). However, when the price variable (X1) is regressed simultaneously with the product quality and promotion variables, all three have a large impact, accounting for 70.2% of purchase interest.

Based on the results of the analysis performed, we know that the most dominant variable influencing Y is variable X2, namely product quality. X2 or product quality variables have a large impact on Y or purchase intent. This can be seen in the calculated t-score $2.643 > t$ Table 1.96. Then the second most important variable, followed by the X3 or promotion variable. Promotional variables also have a large impact on Y or purchase intent. As can be seen from the results of the regression equation, the t-value is $2.879 > t$ table 1.96, and we can conclude that X3 also has a significant effect. Impact on Y. The results and findings of this study are also supported by a study (Lubis, 2018) that found that product quality partially influences purchasing decisions. Proof of the hypothesis allows us to conclude that the higher the product quality of the millennial garden houseplants, the higher the consumer interest in purchasing the millennial garden.

Based on the results of research conducted, the results show a significant impact between advertising and consumer interest in purchasing a millennial garden. This result comes from the regression equation and the calculated t value is $2.879 > t$ table 1.96 and we can conclude that X3 also has a

large effect on Y. The results of this study are also supported by a previous study conducted by Yoebrilanti (2018), who found that the results of the correlation value between advertising variables and consumer willingness to purchase were higher than his 0.658. It is described as obtained by value. By obtaining this value, we can conclude that there is a strong one-way relationship between the two variables. (Ivantan, Khoiriah, and Karmiyati, 2020) explain the same. In other words, advertising strategy has a large impact on purchase interest, regression equation $Y = 9.955 + 0.834X$, implying a correlation value of 0.763. Two variables have a strong influence. Our results, supported by proof of our hypothesis and several previous studies, allow us to conclude that the more intensive advertising is, the more interested millennial garden consumers are in purchasing houseplants increase.

From the results of the coefficient of determination analysis in the table, product quality (X2) has a 53% positive effect on willingness to buy (Y), and sales promotion (X3) has a 36% positive effect on purchasing. It can be concluded that there is is the interest rate (Y) and the price variable is the purchase interest rate (Y)..

Table 8 Operational table of X & Y variables

VARIABLES	DIMENSIONS	INDICATOR
Price	Consumer Price Affordability	1. Feeling no objection to the price set by a product.
		2. Feel that the type and <i>brand</i> of product is inappropriate for the price charged.
	Price Match with Product Quality	1. Do not mind paying more for a better quality product.
		2. Feeling that, as the price is lower, the quality of the product is also lower.
	Price Match with Consumer Benefits	1. Decided to buy the product, because they felt the product had many benefits.
		2. Willing to pay a high price because the benefits of the product are large/ many.
	Price in accordance with ability	1. Consumers consider price, before deciding to buy a product.
		2. Deciding to buy an expensive product, as long as there is a <i>discount</i> .
3. Decided to purchase the product. at a high price, with a periodic payment period.		
Product Quality	Shape	1. The product model looks attractive.
		2. The texture of the product is attractive and pleasant to the touch.
	Performance	1. Products have the best quality assurance.
		2. Product quality is good, but the price is not expensive.
	Conformance to Specifications	1. Products are in line with market trends.
		2. The product matches what the customer wants.
	Resilience	1. The product does not deteriorate despite daily use.
		2. The product is not damaged even if placed in stressful situations.
	Aesthetics	1. The beauty of the product is eye-catching.
		2. The aspects and ornaments in the product make consumers feel happy to see it.
Perceived Quality	1. Product quality is in line with what consumers imagine.	
	2. The product has advantages, in accordance with what consumers expect.	

Promotion	Sales Promotion	1.Communication whose information content attracts the customer's attention. 2. Communication provided, making consumers want to buy.
	Direct Marketing	1. The way of communication makes potential customers immediately want to buy. 2. The way of communication can build a relationship between marketing and potential customers.
	Personal Selling	1. Consumers feel confident about a product. 2. Consumers feel confident in a product.
	Purchase Intention	Attention 1. Consumers research further on a product that is considered to be of interest. 2. Consumers periodically observe products that they find attractive.
	Interest	1. Consumers feel compelled to find out more about a product. 2. Consumers approach a product.
	Desire	1. Consumers feel curious about a product. 2. Feeling like owning a product.

IV. CLOSING

This study was conducted on Millennial Garden ornamental products to test the impact of price, product quality, and promotional variables on purchase intent. The survey focuses on millennial garden buyers and potential buyers, with up to 100 respondents having specific considerations. Based on our analysis and considerations, we can draw the following conclusions: The price variable does not significantly influence the willingness to purchase millennial garden ornaments. Product quality variables have a significant impact on purchase intentions for millennial garden ornaments. Advertising variables have a significant impact on millennial garden décor purchase intentions.

❖ *Managerial Advice*

The research conducted, found that there is an influence between product quality on buying interest. Based on this, activists and sellers of ornamental plants are expected to further improve the quality of ornamental plant products such as improving maintenance, paying attention to appearance (*display*) and pest prevention treatments, especially local ornamental plants, so that they are easy to maintain and not easily attacked by pests.

In addition to improving product quality, ornamental plant business activists also need to increase promotions such as providing *discounts, cashback, buy 1 get 1*, etc. Promotion also needs to be expanded so that more people know and are interested in buying ornamental plants at Millennial Garden. Promotion also needs to be expanded so that more people know and are interested in buying ornamental plants at Millennial Garden.

❖ *Academic Advice*

In future research, it is hoped that this research can be used as a comparison material and also a reference for further research, to deepen information and further research should be carried out on similar topics, but by developing other variables to be involved in research and calculations such as taking into account demographic factors such as age and gender of consumers.

REFERENCES

- [1]. (2006:21), D. d. (2006). factors affecting price. ornamental product, 50-62. Afifah, V. (2013). Analysis of the Marketing Mix of Ornamental Plants at PT Bina Usaha Flora, Sukaresmi District, Cianjur Regency Bogor Agricultural University, 100-106.
- [2]. Asnahwati. (2021). Business Prospects for Ornamental Plants during the Covid 19 Pandemic Perception, Business Prospects and Ornamental Plants, 313-308.
- [3]. Dini Artha Widya Putri, T. D. (2015). Marketing Strategy for Ornamental Plants in Mataran City Marketing Strategies for Ornamental Plants. Ornamental Plants Business Management, 168- 180.
- [4]. Dita Megasari, S. K. (2021). Marketing strategy for ornamental plants during covid 19 at mekarjaya nursery. Proceedings of the National Seminar on Poverty Reduction, 329-340.
- [5]. Dita Megasari, S. K. (2021). Marketing Strategy for Ornamental Plants during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Proceedings of the National Seminar on Poverty Reduction, 329-341.
- [6]. Heriyana, R. (2020). The influence of lifestyle and convenience on students' buying interest in shopping online. journal of business management applications, 1-9.
- [7]. Lubis, N. H. (2019). Analysis of the Effect of Price Product Quality and Lifestyle on purchasing decisions for ornamental plants at cv paris garden medan. journal plants, 1-9.
- [8]. Maulan, H. (2009). Analysis of consumer preferences for anthurium ornamental plants. Bogor agricultural University, 1-69.
- [9]. Raffles, D. (2019). The effect of location and price on purchasing decisions by consumers at the pertiwi flower ornamental plant business in the lubuk minturun village of Padang city according to the perspective of Islamic economics bogor sharia ornamental, 30-40.
- [10]. Rini kuswati, A. s. (2018). Antecedents Of Online Purchasing Behavior Antecedents of online purchasing behavior Benefit journal of business management, 39-48.

- [11]. Rizki Putri Damayanti, A. S. (2021). antecedents of purchasing decisions for ornamental plants during the pandemic in Surakarta. *Business Lantern*,172-181.
- [12]. ROMAN UMBU HAUMARA, I. K. (2016). Marketing Mix of Ornamental Plants. *E-Journal of Agribusiness and Agritourism*, 538-547.
- [13]. Sabitra, Y. R. (2017). Analysis of the effect of product quality price and service quality on customer loyalty. *Institutional Repository*,1-21.
- [14]. Satria, A. A. (2017). The Effect Of Price, Promotion, And Product Quality On Consumer Buying Interest In The A-36 Company Performance Management & Business Startup Journal,1-9.
- [15]. Sri Sepriani Sinaga, D. C. (2011). Analysis Of Cut Flower Marketing Strategy.
- [16]. Fresh Flower, Internal Factors, External Factors, Marketing Strategy,1-13.
- [17]. Yatiman. (2018). Analysis of Factors that influence consumer behavior in purchasing decisions for orchids (orchidachae) at Yusra and widha - wan florist businesses. *bogor ornamentaly*,50- 60.